

Electrometric Studies of UO_2^{++} , Cu^{++} , Ni^{++} , Co^{++} and Mn^{++} Complexes of Tridentate Schiff Base

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The interaction between UO_2^{++} , Cu^{++} , Ni^{++} , Co^{++} and Mn^{++} with 3-aldehydosalicylic acid-p. bromo aniline (3.ASA-p.BA) have been studied in aqueous-dioxane medium potentiometrically by following Bjerrum-Calvin pH titration technique^{1,2}. It is observed that all metals form 1:1 complex with 3.ASA-p.BA as established by conductance measurements and elemental analysis. The ligand is biprotic. The values of $\log K_1H$ and $\log K_2H$ are 9.80 and 3.70 respectively. The order of stability constants is $\text{UO}_2^{++} > \text{Cu}^{++} > \text{Ni}^{++} > \text{Co}^{++} > \text{Mn}^{++}$.

NO work on the reaction of metals with 3.ASA-p.BA is reported in the existing literature. The present investigations are aimed at to determine the composition and stability constants of the UO_2^{++} , Cu^{++} , Ni^{++} , Co^{++} and Mn^{++} complexes with 3.ASA-p.BA derived by the condensation of 3-Aldehydosalicylic Acid and p.bromo aniline.

Materials : All reagents and chemicals used were of Analar/B.D.H. grade.

The purified Dioxane³ and Carbon dioxide free Sodium Hydroxide⁴ were prepared. Perchloric Acid of 0.1M and NaClO_4 of 2M were prepared by the dilution of double distilled water. Metal ions of requisite concentrations were prepared in double distilled water and was estimated by EDTA⁵.

Elico-conductivity Bridge CM-32 was used to determine conductance.

A Metrohm pH meter Model E-350A with wide range glass calomel electrode was used and calibrated at two pH, at 4.01 with potassium hydrogen phthalate and at 7.0 pH with potassium hydrogen phthalate and sodium hydroxide buffers.

The ligand was prepared in the laboratory.

Experimental and Results

1. Synthesis of Ligand : 3-Aldehydosalicylic acid was prepared⁶ and refluxed with p.bromo aniline in unimolar proportions in alcoholic medium. The deep

yellow coloured needles of this Schiff base separate, which are soluble in alcohol and dioxane. It was purified by repeated crystallisation and analysed for their purity before use. The nitrogen estimated by Dumas method.

3-ASA-p.BA = $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_3\text{NBr}$: Yellow fine needles.
Nitrogen = Found \approx 4.28
Calculated \approx 4.37

2. Isolation and analysis of the complexes : The metal complexes were prepared by refluxing calculated amount of corresponding metal acetates and the Schiff base in ethanolic medium on water bath for 2 hrs. Sodium acetate facilitated the complexation in certain cases.

The solids so separated were filtered and washed with aq. ethanol and dried in vacuum desiccator.

Table 1 shows the elemental analysis, compositions and colour of the compounds isolated.

3. Potentiometric Titrations : The following solutions were titrated separately against 0.1 M NaOH solution, keeping total volume as 50.0 ml. in the 30/70(v/v) dioxane-water medium.

- (i) 5.0 ml 0.1M HClO_4 + 5.0 ml 2 M NaClO_4 .
- (ii) 5.0 ml. 0.1M HClO_4 + 5.0 ml NaClO_4 + 5.0 ml 0.005 M Ligand
- (iii) 5.0 ml. 0.1M HClO_4 + 5.0 ml. 2M NaClO_4 + 5.0 ml 0.005 M Ligand + 5.0 ml 0.001 M Metal.

TABLE I

Name of the complex, colour & composition	Analysis			
	Metal		Nitrogen	
	Found	Calculated	Found	Calculated
1-3-ASA-p.BA- UO_2 . $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_4\text{N.Br-UO}_2$ Yellow Colour.	44.32	44.55	2.10	2.31
2-3-ASA-p.BA-Cu. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_4\text{N.Br-Cu}$ Light green yellow.	15.58	15.89	3.42	3.50
3-3-ASA-p.BA-Ni. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_4\text{N Br.-Ni}$ Green colour.	14.41	14.59	3.41	3.54
4-3-ASA-p.BA-Co. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_4\text{N Br.-Co}$ Pink colour.	14.83	14.91	3.46	3.54
5-3-ASA-p.BA-Mn. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_4\text{N.Br.-Mn}$ Dark brown colour.	14.14	14.04	3.61	3.57

The 100 ml. tipless pyrex beakers containing solutions were kept immersed in thermometric bath maintained at $25^\circ \pm 1^\circ$ and kept covered with a perspex cover with holes to admit electrode, burette and the glass stirrer. The pH was noted after the addition of 0.02 ml. of the alkali.

The $\bar{n}A$, \bar{n} and pL were calculated by employing the formula of Irving and Rossotti⁸.

The formation curve was plotted between $\bar{n}A$ and pL to calculate Proton-Ligand stability constants by employing various computational methods⁹ viz. interpolation at half $\bar{n}A$ value, interpolation at various $\bar{n}A$ values and Mid point method. (Table No. 2)

Method	log K_1H	log K_2H	log β
1. Interpolation at half $\bar{n}A$ values	9.82	3.68	13.50
2. Interpolation at various $\bar{n}A$ values	9.76	3.74	13.50
3. Mid point method	9.82	3.68	13.50
Mean	9.80	3.70	13.50

The metal ligand stability constants were calculated by plotting a graph between \bar{n} and pL. The values of log K_1 were directly read from this curve (Table 3).

TABLE 3—METAL LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS OF 3-ASA-P.BA. CHELATES

Metal Ion	log K_1
UO_2^{++}	5.58
Cu^{++}	5.15
Co^{++}	4.91
Ni^{++}	4.88
Mn^{++}	4.77

Discussion

The result reveals that UO_2^{++} , Cu^{++} , Ni^{++} , Co^{++} and Mn^{++} forms 1:1 complex and the sequence of stability is found to be $UO_2^{++} > Cu^{++} > Co^{++} > Ni^{++} > Mn^{++}$ which is in accordance to Irving-Williams¹⁰ except in

the case of Co and Ni. It must be added that inspite of the tendency of metal ions to hydrolyse in aqueous solution such effects have been ignored in this work as the metal chelates are stable in this pH range.

Considering elemental analysis, potentiometric and conductometric results it was found that all metals form 1:1 complex with this ligand.

The probable structure ascertained as under.

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